

FACTORS PRECEDING WORKPLACE DISTRESS AND ITS IMPACT TO THE PERFORMANCE OF EMERGENCY ROOM NURSES

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the factors preceding workplace distress and its impact on ER Nurses' performance in different Eastern Pangasinan hospitals. It tackled their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, and work status. The study utilized the descriptive research design and a survey questionnaire as the primary tools for gathering data. Several statistical tools were used, like frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Scheffe test, and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). The ER nurses are young adults, female-dominated, into marital relationships, did not pursue tertiary education, earn an average salary, and have casual and contractual status. The respondents' stress is highest on management and physical stress and lowest on organizational culture and relationship work stress. The impact of workplace distress on their performance had caused them burn-out and sleep disturbances, short temper, and difficulty concentrating. The younger age bracket experienced organizational culture stress compared to the older ones. Contractual employees claim to have experienced organizational culture stress more than regular employees. Work status affects emergency room nurses' response to time and organizational culture stress. The higher the emergency room nurse's work status, the less time and physical stress they experience. No significant relationship exists between the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses and the rest of the profile variables.

Keywords: *Workplace, Distress, Performance, ER Nurses*

INTRODUCTION

Being a nurse has several difficulties that might lead to stress, burnout, and depression. These difficulties can result in medical errors, hazards to patient safety, and less favorable health results if the correct coping mechanisms are not used. Emergency nurses work in a setting where there is a distinct risk to the safety of patients and clinicians due to the environment's challenges: demand surpassing capacity, a lack of people to handle this need and limited resources. While this has been shown to occur across specialties, emergency nurses are at the most risk, with potential repercussions for patients, organizations, and practitioners.

According to Michael Neenan (2018) of the Center for Stress Management and Cognitive-Behavioral Therapists, stress results from pressures exceeding our ability to cope. Increased stress can harm one's physical health at work and outside. The fight-or-flight response can impair biological functions and make people more susceptible to illness when activated repeatedly. The recurrent production of the stress hormone cortisol, for instance, can compromise immunity and increase the risk of Alzheimer's disease, cardiovascular disease, and autoimmune illnesses. Chronic stress can harm your health by preventing you from engaging in good habits like exercise, a balanced diet, and sleep. Workplace stress can have adverse effects on companies or organizations. Burnout lowers workplace productivity, increases absenteeism and job turnover, fosters workplace conflict, and increases stress in the office. Organizational culture and management may also cause anxiety, including fear-based cultures that leave employees anxious about their performance, ineffective or insufficiently trained leadership, unmanageable workloads, and unaddressed relational issues between colleagues.

One of the groups of employees highly susceptible to workplace distress are those working in hospitals – Doctors and Nurses. A nurse may work in a variety of environments. However, working in hospitals is the most prevalent. In addition to hospitals, nurses have opportunities for employment in settings such as patients' homes, residential care facilities, schools, research environments, and various medical clinics, as well as residential care at schools, research settings, and other medical clinics. They could also work in the public health sector to promote better patient health outcomes in the healthcare system. Most nurses are employed in hospital settings. In this setting, a nurse collaborates with other medical specialists as part of a medical team to give patients the best treatment possible. The nurse's job is to protect the patient's interests and watch for any changes in their health so they can respond appropriately. They frequently follow the instructions of other healthcare professionals who make crucial choices about the treatment of the patients, but they are also involved in the process. They may provide feedback and recommendations to support the patient.

The healthcare workforce is predominantly composed of nurse's health and well-being are affected by the demands of their workplace, and in turn, their well-being affects their work and the people they care for. As it has in so many other areas, COVID-19 has imposed new challenges for nurses' well-being. However, it has also offered opportunities to give nurses' well-being the attention it deserves and to address the systems, structures,

and policies that create workplace hazards and stresses that lead to burnout, fatigue, and poor physical and mental health. Flaubert, J. L., Menestrel, S. L., Williams, D. R., & Wakefield, M. K. (2021, May 11). Because nurses are on the front lines of direct patient care, they are susceptible to a variety of pressures that can adversely affect their physical and mental health.

According to Phillips et al. (2022), emergency nurses are highly susceptible to burnout due to continual exposure to traumatic events, varying work schedules, violence directed at staff, and, in recent times, due to the stressors of the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, Yuwanich et. al. (2017), cited that occupational stress has negative effects on employee's health and organizational productivity. Nurses in emergency department are more exposed to stress than nurses in other departments.

Another factor that triggers the stress to ER nurses is being underpaid and overworked. According to the news of Magsambol (Rappler, 2020), the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), cited an entry-level registered nurse receives an average salary of P8,000 (\$158.54) to P13,500 (\$267.54) per month.

Another factor that stresses nurses is time pressure. According to Goldsby (2020), perceived time pressure is one of the primary sources of stress for nurses. Given the possible adverse effects of perceived time pressures on nurses, a nurse manager's capacity to guide nurses in reducing this pressure and, as a result, help them make better decisions might improve nurses' performance and well-being.

Another factor based on the study of Rosa et al. (2019) is the shift of work, which involves an alteration in psychophysical homeostasis and a decrease in performance. It is an obstacle for social and family relationships, as well as a risk factor for stress, sleep disorders, metabolic disorders, diabetes, cardiovascular disorders, and breast cancer.

Based on the issues mentioned above, the researcher determined the factors that trigger workplace distress and its impact to the performance of ER nurses in selected hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. Since Province of Pangasinan is composed of highly urbanized cities and municipalities, there are many nurses who are suffering from workplace distress while working in different hospitals. Moreover, this study will give recommendations and interventions to lessen the negative impact of workplace distress for the improvement of performance of nurses.

Conceptual/ Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Stress theory of Hans Selye. He theorized that overexposing the body to stress would cause "general adaptation syndrome," which could lead to shock, alarm and eventually exhaustion. Far from being limited to soldiers, the range of potential sufferers included all of humanity (Rothman, 2016).

The Transactional Theory of Stress and Coping, developed by Lazarus and Folkman, provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how individuals perceive and respond to stressors. This theory emphasizes that external events do not

solely determine stress but are also influenced by the individual's appraisal of those events and their perceived ability to cope Berjot, S., & Gillet, N. (2011).

According to the study by Jennings (2008), stress has been classified as an interaction, an outcome or response, and an antecedent or stimulus. It has been examined from a wide range of perspectives. For instance, Hans Selye's physiological evaluation encourages considering the link between stress and sickness. On the other hand, stress was viewed by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) as "a particular relationship between the person and the environment that the person appraises as taxing or exceeding his or her resources and endangering his or her well-being."

According to Jennings (2008), stress has been classified into various perspectives, including an interaction, an outcome or response, and an antecedent or stimulus. This multifaceted view acknowledges the complexity of stress and its impacts. For example, Hans Selye's physiological perspective emphasizes the connection between stress and illness. On the contrary, Lazarus and Folkman (1984) delineated stress as "a specific dynamic between the individual and their surroundings, perceived by the individual as imposing demands or pressures that surpass their available resources, thus posing a threat to their well-being." This emphasizes the subjective assessment of stress within the interplay of the individual and their environment.

Another theory applied in the study is the Sub concept of the Neuman System Model, which considers stressors as any phenomena capable of breaching flexible and regular lines of defense, potentially leading to positive or negative outcomes. Stressors may be intrapersonal - which occurs within the person's system boundary and correlates with the internal environment; Interpersonal – which occurs outside the person's system boundary and has effects on the system, such as the environment; and Extra personal stressors, which occur outside the person's system but in a greater distance than interpersonal stressors such as social policies. When these stressors break the line of defense, the person's system is invaded, lines of resistance are activated, and the stress will occur either positively or negatively.

Aligning with the abovementioned theories, people deal with environmental stress. In a workplace setting, distress is caused by many factors, such as heavy workloads, time pressures, environment, and work shift schedules. In this study, the factors mentioned are being used to assess their impact on ER Nurses' performance and formulate interventions to lessen their adverse effects and improve their perform.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Research Questions

This study determined the factors preceding workplace distress and its impact on ER nurses' performance in selected Eastern Pangasinan hospitals.

Specifically, this study answered the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. age;
 - b. gender;
 - c. civil status;

- d. highest educational attainment
 - e. Work Status, and
 - f. Monthly family income?
2. What are the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses along;
 - a. time stress;
 - b. organizational culture stress;
 - c. management stress;
 - d. physical stress; and
 - e. relationship at work stress?
3. What are the perceived impact of workplace distress on their performance as ER nurses?
4. Is there a significant difference between the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses across their profile variables?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses to their perceived impact of workplace distress to the performance as ER nurses?
6. What intervention program could be proposed to develop effective behaviors to help reduce and manage stress at work?

Null Hypotheses

This study was tested in its null form at 0.05 level of significance that;

1. There is no significant difference between the between the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses across their profile variables
2. There is no significant relationship between the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses across their profile variables.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter provides an overview of the research design and strategy employed, offers insights into the study's population and locality, elucidates the data-gathering tool utilized, expounds upon the data-gathering procedure, and delineates the statistical treatment of data.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study subjects were the Emergency Room Nurses in 5 different public hospitals and an Infirmary clinic in Eastern Pangasinan. ER 50 nurses were involved as respondents and were present when the data gathering was done. The study was conducted during the second semester of 2023-2024.

Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire was utilized to gather data from the respondents. The items found in the questionnaire were taken from several articles and research studies related to the study. However, it was subjected to validation from experts in the nursing field: a

faculty researcher, an instructor, and a nurse administrator in the nursing service. The combined rating was highly valid.

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Data Gathering Tool

The study determined the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress and Its Impact on Emergency Room Nurses' Performance in selected Eastern Pangasinan hospitals. The tool used in gathering the data was a survey questionnaire adapted from different studies and literature related to the study. Part I dealt with the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, and work status. Part II tackled the factors preceding workplace distress and its impact on the performance of ER nurses. Part III focused on the impact of workplace distress on their performances, and Parts IV and IV focused on the significant relationship and differences between the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress and Its Impact on the Performance of Emergency Room Nurses across their profile variables.

The questionnaire was validated by experts in the field of nursing: Professors handling the Research subjects, ER supervisors, and Nursing Faculty. Their suggestions and recommendations were incorporated to further improve the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

After formulating the questionnaire, a letter addressed to the Dean of the Graduate and Advance Studies, asking for permission to conduct the study, will be communicated. As soon as permission was granted, the researcher wrote the respondents and started disseminating questionnaires. The researcher personally used the data-gathering process to answer questions raised by the respondents. Data was gathered during the Second semester of the school year 2023-2024. The data was collected, tabulated, and analyzed upon retrieval of the research instrument.

Treatment of Data

The data collected were tabulated into a contingency table and treated with proper statistical measures.

For problem number 1, the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, work status, and monthly

family income was determined using frequency and percentage. The formula used is as follows:

$$P (\%) = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where; P= percentage equivalent each bracket

f= number of respondents in each bracket

n= total number of respondents

$$WM = \frac{\sum fX}{N}$$

For problem number 2, the weighted mean was used on the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses, along with time stress, organizational culture stress, management stress, physical stress, and relationships at work stress. Also, problem 3 is the respondents' perceived impact of workplace distress on their performance as ER nurses. The formula is as follows:

Where; WM= average of each category

f= number of respondents in each bracket

X=point value classification

n= total number of respondents

A five-point Likert Scale was used in the analysis.

Point Value Classification	Mean Range	Descriptive Equivalent
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50-4.49	Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree

For problem number 4, the significant relationship and difference between the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses across their profile variables, t-test, and One-Way ANOVA were used. The formula for computing the t-test and ANOVA were as follows:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d} - \mu_0}{\frac{S_d}{\sqrt{n}}}, \text{ df} = n - 1$$

Where; \bar{d} = mean of the differences

n = number of sample

S_d = standard deviation of the differences

For One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA):

Source of Variations	SS	Df	MS	Fc
Between Columns	$SS_b = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k T_i^2}{n} - \frac{T^2}{nk}$	$df_b = k - 1$		

			$MSS_b = \frac{SS_b}{df_b}$	$F_c = \frac{MSS_b}{MSS_w}$
Within Columns	$SS_w = SS_t - SS_b$	$df_w = df_t - df_b$	$MSS_w = \frac{SS_w}{df_w}$	
Total	$SS_t = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^2 - \frac{T^2}{nk}$	$df_t = n-1$		

Where; F_c = computed significance value

MSS_b = mean square between columns

MSS_w = mean square within columns

SS_b = sum of squares between columns

SS_w = sum of squares within columns

SS_t = total sum of squares

df_b = degrees of freedom between columns

df_w = degrees of freedom within columns

df_t = total degrees of freedom

k = number of columns

n = sample population

For problem number 5, the Pearson-r formula was used on the significant relationship between the factors preceding workplace stress among ER nurses and their perceived impact of workplace distress on their performance as ER nurses. The formula is as follows:

$$r = \frac{n\sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{[n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Where; $\sum XY$ = sum of the products of X and Y

$\sum X^2$ = sum of the squared values of X

$\sum Y^2$ = sum of the squared values of Y

$\sum X$ = sum of the values of X

$\sum Y$ = sum of the values of Y

Lastly, problem 6 was a proposed stress management program to develop effective behaviors to help reduce and manage stress in the workplace.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the ER nurse respondents.

Part 1. Respondent's Profile

Age. It can be gleaned from the table that the majority of the respondents are in the age bracket of 31-40 years old, with a frequency of 40 or 80 percent, followed by 21-30 years old, with a frequency of 8 or 16 percent, and 41-50 with a frequency of 2 or 4 percent. It revealed that the respondents were young adults. According to Erikson, 31-40 years old are considered young adults. Early adulthood is characterized by the need for young adults to cultivate intimate and affectionate relationships with others. Success in forming these bonds fosters strong connections, while setbacks can lead to feelings of loneliness and isolation. During this phase, individuals actively explore and navigate personal relationships as they transition into adulthood.

Sex. Most respondent nurses were female, with a frequency of 27 or 54 percent, followed by males, with a frequency of 23 or 46 percent. It shows that nursing is still a female-dominated profession. Through the efforts of Florence Nightingale in the mid-nineteenth century, nursing was established as a women's profession.

Civil status. Most respondents were married, with a frequency of 27 or 54 percent, followed by single, with a frequency of 23 or 46 percent. It revealed that the respondents

were into marital relationships and pursuing their experiences in their field of assignment. Being married entails the couple bearing their offspring and forming a family.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents in terms of their Profile Variables
n=50

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
21 – 30	8	16.0
31 – 40	40	80.0
41 – 50	2	4.0
Gender		
Male	23	46.0
Female	27	54.0
Civil Status		
Single	23	46.0
Married	27	54.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	37	74.0
With Master’s units	7	14.0
Master’s Degree	6	12.0
Monthly Family Income (in Php)		
Below P20,000	29	58.0
20,001-30,000	5	10.0
30,001-40,000	11	22.0
40,001-50,000	5	10.0
Wok Status		
Job Order	14	28.0
Contractual	9	18.0
Casual	14	28.0
Regular	13	26.0

Highest educational attainment. It revealed that majority of the respondents were bachelor’s degree holder with a frequency of 37 or 74 percent, followed by those with masteral units with a frequency of 7 or 14 percent, and MAN degree with a frequency of 6 or 12 percent. It showed that majority of the respondents did not pursue higher level of learning. This might be related to the fact that their salaries are not competitive so some nurses fail to enroll in the masteral or doctoral program.

Monthly family program. It showed that most respondents received an income of below P20,000, with a frequency of 29 or 58 percent, P30,001-P40,000 with a frequency of 11 or 22 percent, P20,001-30,000 and P40,001-P50,000 with a frequency

of 5 or 10 percent. It revealed that the respondents received an average monthly income. According to Peria, a socio-economic planning secretary of NEDA, a family of four needs a decent monthly income of P42,000 a month to live above the poverty line (Castillo, 2018).

Work status. It can be gleaned that most of the respondents were Casual and Job order with a frequency of 14 or 28 percent, those regular with a frequency of 13 or 26 percent, and contractual with a frequency of 9 or 18 percent. It reflects that the respondents have no security of tenure in their jobs, and renewable depending on their performance evaluation. As specified in Attorney at Law Journal, Contractual/Job Orders and Casual employees are two distinct employment status of workers in the government based on Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 40 (s. 1998). Distinctions of the two terms based on CSC Memorandum Circular Nos. 40 (s. 1998) and 17-02 (s. 2002).

Part II. Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses

Table 2-7 presents the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress in an Emergency Room Nurses.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are item numbers 1 and 2, “The hours of work are not enough to do all things that must done,” and “I have limited time for my interest/hobbies outside of work,” with a weighted mean of 3.26 and 3.28, or “Moderately Agree.” The respondents somewhat confirm that they experience inadequate time to do their other responsibilities because of work overload. It is a fact that the emergency room (ER) is the first part of the hospital where patients go, and it is always observed that the ER is a busy part of the hospital. At times, inadequate staff is noted where those assigned are overloaded with responsibilities. According to the American Nurses Association (2023), time is critical for a nurse to care for emergency patient situations. Strong time management skills in nursing are also essential to overall health and well-being, including combating stress. Nurses stay on top of their regular responsibilities with a solid strategy while factoring in unexpected circumstances. A well-structured schedule also creates a better work-life balance, so nurses do not spend their free time playing catch-up. Nurses must learn to manage time to ensure the best patient care and work-life harmony.

Table 2
Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency
Room Nurses Along Time Stress
n=50

Indicators	W M	TR
1. The hours of work are not enough to do all things that must done	3.28	MA
2. I have limited time for my interest/hobbies outside of work	3.26	MA
3. I underestimate how long it takes to do things	3.10	MA
4. I rush the process in doing task without ensuring the quality of output	2.44	D

5. I just want to procrastinate.	2.56	MA
	AWM 2.93	MA

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The lowest indicator is item number 4, “I rush the process in doing a task without ensuring the quality of output,” with a weighted mean of 2.44 or “Disagree.” It showed that the ER nurses do not conform to the statement that they do things setting aside the quality of care. Nursing aims to give patients quality nursing care, so nurses maintain that goal for better patient outcomes. Nurses in the ER work very fast because most patients need emergency care, and nurses are aware of that.

Overall, the factors causing workplace distress among emergency room nurses, along with time stress, had an average weighted mean of 2.93, or “Moderately Agree.” It connotes that the ER nurses slightly conform to the indicators. Still, they maintain that the nurses manage their time well to the extent that they extend their duties to finish all the documents needed before the patient is transferred to the ward. Nurses must render care very fast because patients are critical or emergency cases. Nowadays, staffing problems are encountered in many hospitals because many nurses go abroad or look for better job opportunities.

Table 3 presents the factors preceding workplace distress in Emergency Room Nurses along culture stress.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are item numbers 1 and 5, “unable to perform the task as well because of role confusion,” and “that I am unable to participate in decision making,” with a weighted mean of 2.66 and 2.68, or “Moderately Agree.” It reflects that the respondents somewhat confirm that the nurses sometimes got confused due to burnout in their work. The ER is a busy part of the hospital. ER nurses experience it due to the nature of work in the ER, where patients get the first medical management.

Table 3
Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses
Along Organizational Culture Stress
n=50

Indicators	W M	TR
1. Unable to perform task as well because of role confusion.	2.66	MA
2. Uneasy and helpless in solving tasks, when condition comes.	2.60	MA
3. That leadership style is very abusive and inconsiderate.	2.16	D

4. That the organization creates environment of tension, fear and anxiety and can exert unrealistic pressure and control.	2.28	D
5. That I am unable to participate in decision making.	2.68	MA
AWM	2.48	D

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Overall, the factors causing workplace distress among emergency room nurses and culture stress had an average weighted mean of 2.48, or "Disagree." It indicates that the ER nurses do not conform with the indicators mentioned in the factors preceding workplace distress among the ER nurses and culture stress. ANA (2023) cited that a nurse's to-do list begins by evaluating and addressing the hierarchy of needs for patients. That includes ensuring their core physiological needs get met before progressing to additional treatment. Basing care on this tiered system allows the nurse to meet patients' needs in real-time and prioritize decisions.

Table 4 presents the factors preceding workplace distress in Emergency Room Nurses, along with management stress.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are item numbers 2 and 3, "frequently have guilty feelings if I relax and do nothing" and "I often overthink about patient problems even when I am supposed to be relaxing," with a weighted mean of 3.62 and 3.70, or "Agree." It reflects that the respondents ensured that time was well-spent while on duty and maintained their role in giving quality patient care. They have no time to relax because the ER is always busy with severe cases that must be attended to. Most of the time, nurses escape their meals due to work overload.

Table 4
Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses
Along Management Stress
n=50

Indicators	W M	TR
1. There are too many patients' work that are difficult to perform	2.86	MA
2. I frequently have guilty feelings if I relax and do nothing	3.70	A
3. I often over think about patient problems even when I am supposed to be relaxing	3.62	A
4. I feel that I just want to resign due to heavy workloads given by the management	2.94	MA

5. Sometimes I am thinking for resignation and look for other job.	2.94	MA
	AWM	3.21
		MA

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The lowest indicators are items numbers 1, 4, and 5, “there is too much patient work that is difficult to perform,” “Sometimes I am thinking of resignation and looking for another job,” and “I feel that I just want to resign due to heavy workloads given by the management,” with a weighted mean of 2.86 and 2.94, or “Moderately Agree.” It showed that the ER nurses sometimes encountered problems of giving up due to the workload they handled, which made them feel unhappy with their work.

Overall, the factors causing workplace distress among emergency room nurses and management stress had an average weighted mean of 3.21, or “Moderately Agree.” It connotes that the ER nurses slightly confirm that they encounter distress regarding management, although they know it is normal for nurses to be loaded with work while on duty. The finding is similar to the study of Shah (2021), where nurses were predominantly female. Nurses who reported leaving their jobs reported burnout as a reason. Nurses who worked more than 40 hours a week were more likely to identify burnout as a reason they left their jobs. Respondents who reported leaving or considering leaving their jobs owing to burnout reported a stressful work environment and inadequate staffing.

Table 5
Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses
Along Physical Stress
n=50

Indicators	WM	TR
1. Fatigued or tired even when I am supposed to be relaxing.	3.44	MA
2. That my appetite has change, have either a desire to binge or have a loss of appetite/ or skip my meal.	3.06	MA
3. Increase muscular aches and pains especially in the neck, head, lower back, and shoulder.	3.38	MA
4. Mood swings, difficulty making decisions, concentration, and memory impairment.	2.92	MA
5. That my sex drive is lower, can experience hormonal changes such in menstrual cycle, acne, etc.	2.58	MA
	AVM	MA
	3.08	

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicators are item numbers 1 and 3, "fatigued or tired even when I am supposed to be relaxing" and "increase muscular aches and pains especially in the neck, head, lower back, and shoulder" with a weighted mean of 3.44 and 3.38, or "Moderately Agree" It reflects that the ER nurses encounter exhaustion. At the same time, they perform their duties due to the workload needing to be lighter in their areas. Other factors that make them fatigued are related to many consultations and admissions. As mentioned by Jennings (2018), work stress in nursing identified four sources of anxiety among nurses: patient care, decision-making, taking responsibility, and change. The nurse's role has long been regarded as stress-filled based on the physical labor, human suffering, work hours, staffing, and interpersonal relationships central to nurses' work.

The lowest indicator is item number 5, "that my sex drive is lower, can experience hormonal changes such in the menstrual cycle, acne, etc." with a weighted mean of 2.58 or "Moderately Agree." It showed that the ER nurses slightly experience symptoms of hormonal changes since, while on duty, the ER nurse must be free from untoward symptoms so she can focus on the nursing she performs. Sometimes, nurses report for duty even if they do not feel well because of understaffing, and nobody will receive the area. However, nurses are used to it because it is their calling to care for patients.

Overall, the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses, along with physical stress, got an average weighted mean of 3.08, or "Moderately Agree." this implies that the ER nurses encounter tiredness and other manifestations. Still, they ensure they can manage them so their patient care will not be affected. Shah 2021 found in their studies that nurses who reported leaving their current employment reported leaving because of burnout. The hospital setting and working more than 20 hours per week were associated with greater odds of burnout.

Moreover, Table 6 presents the factors preceding workplace distress in an Emergency. Room Nurses along work stress.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicator is item number 2, "that as if listening to my patient/co-workers even though I am preoccupied with my thoughts," with a weighted mean of 2.86, or "Moderately Agree." It reflects that the ER nurse experienced confusion because of the many activities she did for patients, and at times, she missed eating her meals to finish, especially those urgent doctor's orders. According to Jennings (2018), work stress and burnout remain significant concerns among nurses, affecting individuals and organizations. For the individual nurse, regardless of whether stress is

perceived positively or negatively, the neuroendocrine response yields physiologic reactions that may ultimately contribute to illness. In healthcare organizations, work stress may contribute to absenteeism and turnover, which detract from the quality of care.

Table 6
Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses
Along Relationship at Work Stress
n=50

Indicators	WM	TR
1. It so easy to find fault and criticize others rather than praising even if it is deserved.	2.70	MS
2. That as if listening to my patient/co-workers even though I am preoccupied with my own thoughts.	2.86	MA
3. Irritated or angry if the patient/co-worker when they reputedly asked questions.	2.52	MA
4. Unfair or being disrespected among co-employees in terms of treatment.	2.36	MA
5. Mismatch on workplace and my personal values to co-employees.	2.70	MA
AWM	2.63	MA

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The lowest indicator is item 4, “unfair or being disrespected among co-employees in terms of treatment,” with a weighted mean of 2.36 or “Moderately Agree.” It showed that the ER nurses sometimes perceived they were disrespected because everybody was busy. The lowest indicator is item 4, “unfair or being disrespected among co-employees in terms of treatment,” with a weighted mean of 2.36 or “Moderately Agree.” It showed that the ER nurses sometimes perceived they were disrespected because everybody was busy.

Overall, the factors causing workplace distress among emergency room nurses and work stress had an average weighted mean of 2.63, or “Moderately Agree.” It connotes that ER nurses experience different kinds of work-related stress, which is considered normal for nurses because of the work overload they encounter, especially in the emergency room. Nurses encounter much stress but are ready to fight it away to give their nursing care.

Summary of Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses

Table 7 presents the factors preceding workplace distress among Emergency Room Nurses.

As gleaned from the table, among the factors preceding workplace distress among ER nurses, the highest areas of stress are management and physical stress, with a weighted mean of 3.21 and 3.08. It reflects that it affected them more since they encountered fatigue, had muscular pains, and due to heavy workloads, at times, they thought of resigning from their jobs. According to Thompson (2023), stress among nurses is one of the most underappreciated yet impactful issues nurses face. It happens in a nurse's work and personal life. The emotional demands are boundless, and the physical demands/fatigue can be burdensome. This stress often affects the health of nurses and sometimes even the outcomes of patients and patient care.

Table 7
Summary of Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses
n=50

Aspect	WM	TR
Time Stress	2.93	MA
Organizational Culture Stress	2.48	MA
Management Stress	3.21	MA
Physical Stress	3.08	MA
Relationship at Work Stress	2.63	MA
OWM	2.86	MA

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Organizational culture stress is the lowest factor preceding workplace distress, with a weighted mean of 2.48. The study revealed that ER nurses consider this the lowest because they love their work even if their salaries are not comparable to those of other nurses, especially those in the government sector. Nurses are patient in their work because this is their bread and butter and learning experience.

Overall, the factors causing workplace distress among emergency room nurses resulted in a weighted mean of 2.86, or "Moderately Agree." It implies that ER nurses experience reasonable types of stress while they are in the workplace. Stress contributes to the growth of nurses since it is a regular occurrence while on duty. As mentioned in the article of Advent Health University (2020), stress can lead to poor sleep, contributing to

more stress. Eating healthy foods and exercising can help break the cycle. Finding time to exercise can be difficult, mainly when nurses already work long hours doing physically demanding work, but the benefits are substantial. Exercise releases endorphins and boosts serotonin levels, improving mood, appetite, and sleep cycles.

Part III. Perceived Impact of Workplace Distress to the Performance of Emergency Room Nurses

Table 8 presents the perceived impact of workplace distress on the performance of ER nurses.

Table 8
Perceived Impact of Workplace Distress to the Performance of Emergency Room Nurses
n=50

Indicators	WM	TR
Workplace distress causes me to feel ...		
1. Job burn-out on the tasks that I am assigned.	2.86	MA
2. Low self-esteem in myself and to other colleagues and clients.	2.88	MA
3. Lacking of attention on my work.	2.64	MA
4. Having frequent absenteeism.	2.18	D
5. Irritated most of the time.	2.20	D
6. Depressed or having anxiety.	2.38	D
7. I am ill or having a disease.	2.50	MA
8. To loss my productivity.	2.48	D
9. Having low performance quality and output.	2.34	D
10. Having sleep disturbances, short temper, and difficulty concentrating.	3.24	MA
AVM	2.57	MA

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.50 – 4.49	Agree (A)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)

As gleaned from the table, the highest among the indicators are items numbers 1 and 2, “job burn-out on the tasks that I am assigned,” and “low self-esteem in myself and to other colleagues and clients,” with a weighted mean of 2.86 and 2.88, or “Moderately Agree.” It revealed that it has a significant impact on burnout in their duties, and the feeling of having low self-confidence may be related to being overworked. Nurses are used to encountering stress, and they know what to do to relieve their stress. They are adjustable to any situation they meet in the area, especially in the emergency room.

The respondents disagreed on frequent absenteeism, being irritated, having anxieties, losing productivity, and having low-performance quality with a descriptive equivalent of “Disagree.” As a nurse, frequent absences are not allowed unless excusable because the out-gong shift will be affected since nobody will receive the endorsement. There are feelings of anxiety, but that is only temporary since nurses can quickly adapt to any situation while on duty.

Overall, the impact of workplace distress on the performance of ER nurses got an average weighted mean of 2.57 or “Moderately Agree.” It connotes that the ER nurses perceived the impact of work-related stress as reasonable because it is part of their duty to experience stress on duty. As cited in the article at Advent Health University (2023), nurses’ negative emotions, such as fear, anxiety, or frustration, are often concealed to project the compassion, confidence, and professionalism necessary to perform their jobs. Such dissonance between feelings and outer appearances can contribute significantly to mental fatigue and stress.

Part IV. Differences in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress Among Emergency Room Nurses

Table 9-16 shows the differences in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurse.

Table 9 presents the computed F-values along time stress, management stress, physical stress and relationship at work stress provided significance values which are higher than the set .05 level of significance.

Table 9
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Time Stress	Between Groups	1.635	2	.817	1.547	.223	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.826	47	.528			
	Total	26.461	49				
Organizational Culture Stress	Between Groups	3.832	2	1.916	4.873	.012	Significant
	Within Groups	18.479	47	.393			
	Total	22.311	49				
Management Stress	Between Groups	.982	2	.491	.840	.438	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.451	47	.584			
	Groups						

	Total	28.433	49				
Physical Stress	Between Groups	.700	2	.350			Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.651	47	.524	.668	.518	
	Total	25.351	49				
Relationship at Work Stress	Between Groups	1.910	2	.955			Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.771	47	.463	2.061	.139	
	Total	23.681	49				
Overall	Between Groups	1.481	2	.741			Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.925	47	.360	2.057	.139	
	Total	18.406	49				

This leads to acceptance of the null hypothesis. Significant difference exists along organizational culture stress. Their age affects relationship at work that causes distress among emergency room nurses. As compared to the older nurses, the young ones are still adapting to the conditions in the ER since they are in the service for few years. Gradually they will learn to adapt to any challenges encountered in caring for different types of patients.

Table 10
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses across Age

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Organizational Culture Stress	21-30 vs 31-40	.755	.012

A significant positive mean difference exists between 21-30 and 31-40 nurses. The younger age bracket has been experiencing organizational culture stress compared to the older ones.

This might be related to their experience since they are still in the service for a few years, learning to adapt to their work environment compared to the older nurses. They are earning their experiences, but once they master all the ER competencies, they will slowly learn to know the ins and outs of the ER.

Table 11 presents the difference in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses across genders.

Table 11
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress
among Emergency Room Nurses across Gender

Aspect	Gender	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	Df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Time Stress	Male	23	2.91						Not Significant
	Female	27	2.94	-.028	.211	48	-.131	.896	
Organizational Culture Stress	Male	23	2.40						Not Significant
	Female	27	2.54	-.141	.192	48	-.732	.468	
Management Stress	Male	23	3.31						Not Significant
	Female	27	3.13	.187	.217	48	.863	.392	
Physical Stress	Male	23	3.09						Not Significant
	Female	27	3.07	.020	.206	48	.098	.922	
Relationship at Work Stress	Male	23	2.68						Not Significant
	Female	27	2.59	.093	.199	48	.468	.642	
Overall	Male	23	2.88						Not Significant
	Female	27	2.85	.026	.176	48	.150	.881	

The computed t-values suggest acceptance of the null hypothesis. Male and female emergency room nurses experience the same types of stress that precede their workplace distress. Male and female nurses experience the same hardships in attending to patients in the emergency room. Too much stress is encountered in the ER because it is the first step when a patient goes to the hospital. Not only are patients attended to, but including relatives and significant others who are with them. Sometimes, there are very demanding watchers to the extent that they even demand so many things from the nurses.

Table 12 shows the difference in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses across civil status. All the computed t-values have generated significance values higher than the set .05 significance level.

Table 12
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress
among Emergency Room Nurses across Civil Status

Aspect	Gender	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Significance	Remarks
Time Stress	Single	23	2.88			48	-.438	.663	Not Significant
	Married	27	2.97	-.092	.210				
Organizational Culture Stress	Single	23	2.40			48	-.732	.468	Not Significant
	Married	27	2.54	-.141	.192				
Management Stress	Single	23	3.20			48	-.102	.919	Not Significant
	Married	27	3.22	-.022	.218				
Physical Stress	Single	23	3.08			48	.020	.944	Not Significant
	Married	27	3.07	.004	.206				
Relationship at Work Stress	Single	23	2.52			48	-.998	.324	Not Significant
	Married	27	2.72	-.197	.197				
Overall	Single	23	2.82			48	-.511	.612	Not Significant
	Married	27	2.91	-.090	.175				

Therefore, there is no significant difference in the time stress, organizational culture stress, management stress, physical stress, and relationship-at-work stress experienced by the emergency room nurses. The civil status of the nurses does not affect these factors preceding their workplace distress, implying that single and married nurses experience the same stress. Nurses attend to the same tasks while attending patients in the ER. They attend to different types of patients. Some are critical, and some need emergency care.

Table 13 displays the test results of the difference in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses across the highest educational attainment.

Table 13
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress
among Emergency Room Nurses across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Time Stress	Between Groups	.538	2	.269	.488	.617	Not Significant
	Within Groups	25.922	47	.552			
	Total	26.461	49				
Organizational Culture Stress	Between Groups	.082	2	.041	.086	.917	Not Significant
	Within Groups	22.229	47	.473			
	Total	22.311	49				
Management Stress	Between Groups	.669	2	.335	.567	.571	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.763	47	.591			
	Total	28.433	49				
Physical Stress	Between Groups	.546	2	.273	.517	.600	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.805	47	.528			
	Total	25.351	49				
Relationship at Work Stress	Between Groups	.450	2	.225	.456	.637	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.230	47	.494			
	Total	23.681	49				
Overall	Between Groups	.319	2	.160	.414	.663	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.087	47	.385			
	Total	18.406	49				

The computed F-values generated significance values that were all higher than the set .05 significance level. Nurses experience the same effect of time, organizational, management, physical, and relationship-at-work stress and are unaffected by the educational background nurse. It implies that regardless of the academic qualifications of the nurses, they experience different types of stress. When nurses are employed in the emergency room, they are expected to be equipped with the competencies needed in the ER since they undergo related seminars on emergency nursing.

Table 14 presents the difference in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses across monthly family income. All the computed F-values have generated significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance.

Suggests acceptance of the null hypothesis. No significant difference exists in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses, especially when monthly income is considered. It implies that nurses render the utmost care to their patients regardless of their salaries. They render the needed care to all patients admitted to the ER as part of their nursing responsibilities. Nurses patiently give their care when they are in front of patients.

Table 14
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses across Monthly Family Income

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Time Stress	Between Groups	.590	3	.197	.350	.790	Not Significant
	Within Groups	25.871	46	.562			
	Total	26.461	49				
Organizational Culture Stress	Between Groups	.354	3	.118	.247	.863	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.957	46	.477			
	Total	22.311	49				
Management Stress	Between Groups	.169	3	.056	.092	.964	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.264	46	.614			
	Total	28.433	49				
Physical Stress	Between Groups	.551	3	.184	.341	.796	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.800	46	.539			
	Total	25.351	49				
Relationship at Work Stress	Between Groups	.933	3	.311	.629	.600	Not Significant
	Within Groups	22.748	46	.495			
	Total	23.681	49				

Overall	Between Groups	.230	3	.077			
	Within Groups	18.176	46	.395	.194	.900	Not Significant
	Total	18.406	49				

Table 15 discloses the test results for differences in the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses across work status. No significant difference exists between engagement stress, physical stress, and relationship-at-work stress.

However, significant differences exist between time and organizational culture stress across work statuses. Work status affects how emergency room nurses respond to time stress and organizational culture stress. This implies that nurses are significantly affected in the ER because most patients go there, sometimes making them think of filing their leave of absence or resigning from their jobs because of job burnout.

Table 15
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses across Work Status

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Time Stress	Between Groups	5.838	3	1.946			
	Within Groups	20.623	46	.448	4.341	.009	Significant
	Total	26.461	49				
Organizational Culture Stress	Between Groups	4.803	3	1.601			
	Within Groups	17.508	46	.381	4.207	.010	Significant
	Total	22.311	49				
Management Stress	Between Groups	2.474	3	.825			
	Within Groups	25.958	46	.564	1.462	.237	Not Significant
	Total	28.433	49				
Physical Stress	Between Groups	3.785	3	1.262			
	Within Groups	21.566	46	.469	2.691	.057	Not Significant
	Total	25.351	49				
Relationship at Work Stress	Between Groups	1.440	3	.480			
	Within Groups	22.240	46	.483	.993	.404	Not Significant
	Total						

	Total	23.681	49				
Overall	Between Groups	3.193	3	1.064			
	Within Groups	15.214	46	.331	3.218	.031	Significant
	Total	18.406	49				

Nurses come and go in the hospital because they sometimes look for better job opportunities. It is a fact that nurses' salaries are not competitive compared to other professionals. Most nurses apply abroad for better wages and to contribute to their quality of life.

Table 16 shows the results of the Scheffe test to determine the groups that have demonstrated significant differences along time stress and organizational culture stress across work status.

Table 16
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses across Work Status

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Time Stress	Contractual vs Casual	.862	.039
	Contractual vs Regular	.918	.027
Organizational Culture Stress	Contractual vs Regular	.920	.014
Overall	Contractual vs Regular	.745	.041

The significant positive mean difference indicates that the first group in the compared groups has higher mean values than the second group. This means that contractual employees have experienced greater time stress than casual and regular employees.

Meanwhile, contractual employees have experienced organizational culture stress more than regular employees. It implies that those contractual employees think that since they are not regular in their jobs, they have the mentality that they can be removed from the service depending on their performance. They felt they had no tenure security, contributing to their stress and sometimes affecting their job performance.

Part V. Relationship Between the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses and their Profile Variables

Table 17 shows the relationship between the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses and their profile variables. A significant relationship exists between time stress, work status, and physical stress with work status.

Relationship Between the Factors Preceding Workplace Distress among Emergency Room Nurses and their Profile Variables

TABLE 17	Time Stress		Organizational Culture Stress		Management Stress		Physical Stress		Relationship at Work Stress	
	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig
Age	-.245	.087	-.330*	.019	-.180	.210	-.153	.289	-.245	.086
Gender	.019	.896	.105	.468	-.124	.392	-.014	.922	-.067	.642
Civil Status	.063	.663	.105	.468	.015	.919	-.003	.984	.143	.324
Highest Educational Attainment	-.089	.539	-.054	.710	-.140	.334	-.140	.331	.020	.892
Monthly Family Income	.092	.525	.083	.566	.017	.907	.052	.720	.178	.217
Work Status	-.332*	.018	-.160	.266	.154	.284	-.282*	.047	-.079	.586

The negative R- R-values indicate an indirect relationship. The higher the work status of the emergency room nurse, the less time stress and physical stress they experience. No significant relationship exists between the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses and the rest of the profile variables. This implies that ER nurses seldom encounter stress when busy with their tasks since they are much more focused on their work. We know that nurses work very fast to revive or give emergency care to clients. Once a nurse is in front of their patients, they are so empathetic and want faster recovery.

PROPOSED STRESS MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

General objectives: The proposed intervention program will equip employees with practical tools and strategies to effectively manage workplace stress, enhance resilience, and promote overall well-being. They are designed to improve the ER nurses' wellness program to cope with and minimize work-related stress.

Activity	Objective	Time Table
<p>1. Educational workshops</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To conduct workshops covering topics such as awareness, identifying stressors, understanding the physiological and psychological effects of stress, and developing coping strategies. • Provide education on the importance of work-life balance, time management, and boundary setting to prevent burnout. 	<p>January 2025</p>
<p>2. Mindfulness and Relaxation Techniques</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer mindfulness meditation sessions to teach employees relaxation techniques, deep breathing exercises, and mindful practices to reduce stress levels and promote emotional regulation 	<p>March 2025</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide resources such as guided meditation recordings and mindfulness apps for ongoing practice. 	
<p>3. Stress Reduction Activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize stress-reduction activities such as yoga classes, tai chi sessions, or nature walks to promote physical activity, relaxation, and stress relief. • Encourage participation in recreational activities and hobbies outside of work to promote leisure and enjoyment. 	<p>May 2025</p>
<p>4. Employees Assistance Program (EAP)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement an EAP to provide confidential counseling services and support for employees experiencing personal or work-related stressors, mental health challenges, or life difficulties. • Ensure access to qualified counselors or therapists who can provide 	<p>July 2025</p>

	individualized support and referrals as needed.	
5. Social support and connection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster a supportive work environment by encouraging peer support networks, team-building activities, and opportunities for social connection. • Facilitate open communication channels and encourage employees to seek support from colleagues, supervisors, or HR personnel when needed. 	September 2025
6. Wellness Resources and Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide access to resources such as self-help books, online articles, and wellness newsletters addressing stress management, resilience building, and work-life balance. 	November 2025

Expected Outcomes

- Increased awareness and understanding of workplace stress among ER nurses.
- Improved ability to identify and manage stressors effectively.
- Enhanced utilization of stress management techniques and coping strategies.
- Reduced absenteeism and turnover rates among ER nursing staff.
- Enhanced overall well-being, job satisfaction, and resilience among ER nurses.
- Creation of a supportive work environment that promotes open communication and mutual support.

Implementing this holistic stress management program will equip ER nurses with the essential tools and resources needed to excel in their demanding roles while prioritizing their health and well-being. By working collaboratively, we aspire to cultivate a resilient and supportive workplace culture that enhances patient care and promotes overall staff satisfaction. Together, we can create an environment where nurses feel empowered, supported, and valued, ultimately leading to improved outcomes for patients and caregivers.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following are now concluded:

The ER nurses are young adults, female-dominated, into marital relationships, did not pursue post-graduate education, earn an average salary, are mostly casuals, and have contractual status.

The respondents' stress is highest on management and physical stress and lowest on organizational culture and relationship work stress.

The impact of workplace distress on their performance has caused burnout, sleep disturbances, short temper, and difficulty concentrating.

The younger age bracket experienced organizational culture stress compared to the older ones. Contractual employees claim to have experienced organizational culture stress more than regular employees. Work status affects emergency room nurses' response to time and organizational culture stress.

The higher the emergency room nurse's work status, the less time and physical stress they experience. No significant relationship exists between the factors preceding workplace distress among emergency room nurses and the rest of the profile variables.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions offered, the following are at this moment proposed:

To be promoted to a regular position, ER nurses must continue earning experience in the area and upgrading their qualifications.

The respondents must improve their performance in the ER for management to have a reason to encourage them to higher positions and relieve their management stress.

The respondents must undergo wellness programs to relieve their burnout and physical distress.

The ER nurses, regardless of their employment status, must continue with their work to minimize their stress in the workplace.

The proposed intervention program can be adapted and implemented to relieve them of workplace distress and improve their performance in the ER

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research on "Factors Preceding Workplace Distress and Its Impact on the Performance of Emergency Room Nurses" adheres rigorously to ethical standards for conducting research involving human participants. Ethical integrity was maintained throughout the study. Through the implementation of the following measures:

Informed Consent: All participating emergency department nurses will get thorough information about the study's goals, methods, possible risks, and advantages before their involvement. Each participant provided written consent, confirming their voluntary participation, and understanding of their rights.

Voluntary Participation: The study will be conducted only with the consent of nurses, who will be guaranteed the freedom to leave the study at any moment without repercussions.

Confidentiality: Safety precautions will be taken to protect participants' anonymity and privacy. Any identifiable information gathered from individual nurses will be anonymized to protect their privacy and treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Avoidance of Harm: To reduce the possibility of injury or discomfort to the attendees. Researchers will ensure that the questions asked in surveys or interviews are non-intrusive and considerate of the nurses' mental health.

Beneficence: The study intends to provide important insights into the elements that emergency department nurses experience before experiencing professional stress. Offering ways to reduce workplace stress and improve nursing performance is designed to help individuals and the larger healthcare community.

Approval: To guarantee adherence to ethical standards, the appropriate institution will examine and approve the research protocol, including the study design, recruiting processes, and data-collecting techniques.

Transparency: The study results will be truthful and open, guaranteeing that they are not altered or distorted to further any goal.

Respect for Participants: Throughout the study, participants' autonomy and rights will be respected, and researchers will handle them with dignity and respect.

Benefit-Risk Assessment: A comprehensive evaluation of the possible advantages and disadvantages of research participation will be carried out, and suitable strategies will be implemented to optimize benefits and reduce disadvantages for participants.

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